

Quantitative equilibrium studies on mixed ligand complexes of nickel-, copper- and zinc(II) with some nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands

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A quantitative study on metal-ligand equilibria involving Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} and 1,2-dihydroxybenzene (ca), 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid (nn) or 8-amino-1-naphthol-3,6-disulfonic acid (an) has been made in solution at 25° and at ionic strength of 0.10 M (KNO₃). Formation of the different complex species has been inferred, and the corresponding equilibrium constants have been evaluated and discussed.

In spite of the extremely rapid development of coordination chemistry, the equilibrium studies of nitrogen and oxygen donor molecules with metal ions have not yet reached maturity. Interesting results have earlier been reported^{1,2} on the complex formation reactions of oxygen, nitrogen and oxygen-nitrogen mixed donor ligands. Expecting some useful information on mixed ligand complexes of such ligands a detailed pH-metric study involving 1,2-dihydroxybenzene (ca), 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid (nn) and 8-amino-1-naphthol-3,6-disulfonic acid (an) and metal ions Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} has been made at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.10 M (KNO₃) and the results are discussed.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation constants :

Existence of proton-ligand equilibria corresponding to dissociation of two protons from each ligand, two phenolic groups of ca and one amino and one phenolic group of nn (mono sodium salt) or an (disodium salt) is evident from their titration curves (Fig. 1 ca and nn systems, an system omitted). The colour change in the titration mixtures also favour proton dissociation from the ligands. Steep inflection at $a = 0$ in the titration curves of nn or an suggests that two protons in each system are liberated in steps, respectively from protonated amino group and the phenolic group. The evaluated proton-ligand dissociation constants of ca ($K_1^H = 10^{-9.38 \pm 0.02}$, $K_2^H = 10^{-11.58 \pm 0.03}$) and nn ($K_1^H = 10^{-2.83 \pm 0.01}$, $K_2^H = 10^{-8.86 \pm 0.03}$) are comparable with literature values²⁻⁴. The proton-ligand dissociation constants corresponding to the protonated amino and phenolic groups of an are $10^{-4.16 \pm 0.02}$ and $10^{-8.51 \pm 0.04}$, respectively.

Binary complexes :

A comparison of pH vs a curves of a ligand and the cor-

Fig. 1. pH vs a curves of Cu^{II}-nn-ca systems

responding 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand systems indicates formation of binary complexes (Fig. 1 pH vs a curves of ca and nn with Cu^{II}, others omitted). Beyond $a = 2.0$ and 1.0, respectively, in ca and nn or an systems, a number of hydroxo complexes also exist in solution.

The complexing tendency of the metal ions follows the order : (i) Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} (ca and nn systems) and (ii) Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} (an system) The K_1 values are greater than the corresponding K_2 values in all the systems except in Cu^{II}-nm system ($\log K_1 = 5.39$ and $\log K_2 = 6.08$). Comparing the values of equilibrium constants (Table 1), it is concluded that the complexing tendency of the ligands with each metal ion under investigation follows the order : ca

Table 1. Equilibrium constants of binary, hydroxo and ternary complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}Temp. = 25°, μ = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Reaction	log K		
	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ ⇌ M(ca)	8.95 ± 0.04	12.65 ± 0.02	9.92 ± 0.02
M(ca) + ca ²⁻ ⇌ M(ca) ₂ ²⁻	5.58 ± 0.06	9.62 ± 0.01	7.69 ± 0.02
M(ca) + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(OH) ⁻	4.19 ± 0.06	6.63 ± 0.03	3.78 ± 0.01
M(ca) ₂ ²⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(ca) ₂ (OH) ³⁻	3.40 ± 0.02	3.68 ± 0.06	—
M ²⁺ + nn ²⁻ ⇌ M(nn)	3.74 ± 0.01	5.39 ± 0.05	4.89 ± 0.03
M(nn) + nn ²⁻ ⇌ M(nn) ₂ ²⁻	3.64 ± 0.01	6.08 ± 0.02	4.68 ± 0.04
M(nn) + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(nn)(OH) ⁻	5.00 ± 0.02	7.29 ± 0.01	5.98 ± 0.01
M(nn)(OH) ⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(nn)(OH) ₂ ²⁻	3.53 ± 0.03	3.84 ± 0.03	3.64 ± 0.02
Mn(nn) ₂ ²⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(nn) ₂ (OH) ³⁻	4.95 ± 0.04	3.00 ± 0.03	4.38 ± 0.02
M(nn) ₂ (OH) ³⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(nn) ₂ (OH) ₂ ⁴⁻	3.30 ± 0.03	2.90 ± 0.04	3.36 ± 0.02
M ²⁺ + an ³⁻ ⇌ M(an) ⁻	7.93 ± 0.02	8.37 ± 0.09	7.42 ± 0.02
M(an) ⁻ + an ³⁻ ⇌ M(an) ₂ ⁴⁻	5.99 ± 0.05	6.25 ± 0.06	5.17 ± 0.02
M(an) ⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(an)(OH) ²⁻	5.75 ± 0.08	7.74 ± 0.02	6.65 ± 0.04
M(an)(OH) ²⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(an)(OH) ₂ ³⁻	—	6.83 ± 0.01	5.84 ± 0.02
M(an)(OH) ₂ ³⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(an)(OH) ₃ ⁴⁻	—	3.87 ± 0.05	—
M(an) ₂ ⁴⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(an) ₂ (OH) ⁵⁻	—	5.75 ± 0.03	5.07 ± 0.02
M(an) ₂ (OH) ⁵⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(an) ₂ (OH) ₂ ⁶⁻	—	—	3.75 ± 0.01
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + nn ²⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(nn) ²⁻	12.91 ± 0.07	18.25 ± 0.09	15.07 ± 0.01
M(ca) + nn ²⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(nn) ²⁻	3.96	5.60	5.15
M(nn) + ca ²⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(nn) ²⁻	9.17	12.86	10.18
M(ca)(nn) ²⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(nn)(OH) ³⁻	3.19 ± 0.05	4.00 ± 0.04	3.08 ± 0.03
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + an ³⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(an) ³⁻	16.97 ± 0.10	21.12 ± 0.06	17.41 ± 0.09
M(ca) + (an) ³⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(an) ³⁻	8.02	8.47	7.49
M(an) ⁻ + ca ²⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(an) ³⁻	9.04	12.75	9.99
M(ca)(an) ³⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(an)(OH) ⁴⁻	4.15 ± 0.02	5.98 ± 0.05	3.44 ± 0.06
M(ca)(an)(OH) ⁴⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(ca)(an)(OH) ₂ ⁵⁻	—	4.08 ± 0.03	—
M ²⁺ + nn ²⁻ + an ³⁻ ⇌ M(nn)(an) ³⁻	11.84 ± 0.07	13.91 ± 0.08	12.46 ± 0.09
M(nn) + an ³⁻ ⇌ M(nn)(an) ³⁻	8.10	8.52	7.57
M(an) ⁻ + nn ²⁻ ⇌ M(nn)(an) ³⁻	3.91	5.54	5.04
M(nn)(an) ³⁻ + OH ⁻ ⇌ M(nn)(an)(OH) ⁴⁻	4.19 ± 0.04	5.08 ± 0.04	4.39 ± 0.03

> an > nn. The oxygen donor ca behaves as a stronger chelating molecule than the mixed nitrogen-oxygen donors nn and an. Smallest values of equilibrium constant for nn complexes than the corresponding values for ca or an complexes may be regarded as a result of its poor electron donating property due to the large size of the ligand (as compared to ca) and electron-withdrawing nature of the sulfonic acid group at *para* position of the phenolic group. A higher charge on an also favours larger metal-ligand interaction, resulting the higher equilibrium constant than that in the corresponding nn systems. The values of ca complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} are comparable with that reported earlier by other workers^{3,5,6}

Table 1 shows that association of OH⁻ ions with 1 : 1 metal-ligand complex of each metal studied follows the

order : M(an)⁻ > M(nn) > M(ca). Here, it may be said that the coordination of OH⁻ ion is favoured in the complexes with mixed nitrogen-oxygen donors, where electron density around the central atom is lower than that in oxygen donor complexes. Further, coordination of OH⁻ ion with mono-hydroxo complexes of Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} is much favoured in an system as compared to that in nn system.

Coordination order of OH⁻ ions with 1 : 2 metal-ligand complexes are : Ni(nn)₂²⁻ > Ni(ca)₂²⁻; Cu(an)₂⁴⁻ > Cu(nn)₂²⁻ > Cu(ca)₂²⁻; Zn(an)₂⁴⁻ > Zn(nn)₂²⁻; and Zn(an)₂(OH)⁵⁻ > Zn(nn)₂(OH)³⁻. The low values of equilibrium constants in the systems of oxygen donor ligand can again be explained on the similar ground as in 1 : 1 metal-ligand systems.

In most of the systems, given below, coordination of

OH⁻ ion with simple or hydroxo complexes of different metal ions involving the same ligand shows the expected orders of stability constants : Cu(ca) > Ni(ca) > Zn(ca); Cu(nn) > Zn(nn) > Ni(nn); Cu(an)⁻ > Ni(an)⁻ > Zn(an)⁻; Cu(nn)(OH)⁻ > Zn(nn)(OH)⁻ > Ni(nn)(OH)⁻; Cu(an)(OH)²⁻ > Zn(an)(OH)²⁻; Cu(an)₂(OH)⁵⁻ > Zn(an)₂(OH)⁵⁻; Ni(nn)₂²⁻ > Zn(nn)₂²⁻ > Cu(nn)₂²⁻; Zn(nn)₂(OH)³⁻ > Cu(nn)₂(OH)³⁻; and Cu(ca)₂²⁻ > Ni(ca)₂²⁻.

Mixed ligand complexes :

The 1 : 1 : 1 mixture of each metal with pair of ligands ca-nn, ca-an or nn-an remains in clear solution in the entire pH range of titration. The colour changes are not very specific, but the presence of mixed ligand complex is inferred from a comparison of the titration curves of the two ligands and their binary complexes with that of the ternary complex (Fig. 1, Cu^{II}-nn-ca system, others omitted). The presence of strong or weak inflections (except in an-nn systems with Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} which show no inflection) at *a* = 2.0 and 3.0 in pH vs *a* curves of all systems of nn-an and ca-nn or ca-an, respectively, also indicates the formation of mixed ligand complexes.

Table I shows that complexing tendency of ligand pairs with each metal ion follows the order : ca-an > ca-nn > nn-an. Similarly, the chelating tendency of these metal ions with each pair of ligand follows the order : Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II}. Also, formation constants for addition of one of the ligands to 1 : 1 metal complex with the other ligand are slightly higher (from 0.07 to 0.32 logarithm units) than *K*₁ values for the addition of the ligand to aquation. These informations are in agreement with those reported by Perrin *et al.*⁷ on ternary complexes of some biologically important ligands, ethylenediamine, histamine, serine and salicylic acid with Cu^{II} ion. A parallel effect has been reported on addition of salicylic acid (sa) to 1 : 1, Th^{IV}- or UO₂^{II}-5-sulfosalicylic acid (ss) or addition of ss to 1 : 1, Th^{IV}- or UO₂^{II}-sa complexes². But, for the reaction, CuA²⁺ + B²⁻ = CuAB (where, A = 2,2'-bipyridyl and B = anion of salicylic acid or catechol), Condike and Martell³ reported higher values of stepwise formation constants (from 0.9 to 1.5 logarithm unit) than for the addition of B to the hydrated Cu^{II} ion. The order of stability constants for coordination of OH⁻ ion with mixed ligand complex of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} involving the pair of ligands ca-nn, ca-an and nn-an, respectively is Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II}. As expected the equilibrium constant value for Cu^{II} ion complex with each ligand pair system is the highest.

Formation of Cu^{II} mixed ligand complex with ca-nn is

also supported by the isolation of Na₂[Cu(ca)(nn)(H₂O)₂].2H₂O. Metal-ligand association through phenolic group of ligand in the complex is exhibited by medium but broad IR band at 522 cm⁻¹. Similarly, very weak but sharp band at 405 cm⁻¹ is due to ν_{Cu-N} vibrations⁸. Coordination of water is supported by presence of bands at 3433 (ν_{OH} strong, broad), 1633 (δ_{O-H} medium, broad) and 850 cm⁻¹ (rocking vibration weak, sharp). A medium but sharp band at 638 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the ν_{Cu-O} vibration of coordinated water. Two more significant bands at 1382 (strong, sharp) and 1049 cm⁻¹ (strong, very sharp) are attributed to asymmetric and symmetric ν_{S-O} vibrations, respectively. The proton magnetic resonance spectrum of the compound recorded in D₂O, displays multiplet signal at δ 7.81–8.99, attributed to aromatic ring protons. The signal at δ 4.76 is due to HOD arising from exchange of protons bonded to hetero atoms with solvent.

Experimental

Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} nitrate solutions were prepared. Metal contents were estimated by usual methods. Aqueous solution of ca (B.D.H.) and an (disodium salt, C.D.H.) were prepared by direct weighing. The volume was raised to get 0.005 *M* concentration of each ligand. nn was purified by dissolving in aqueous alkali medium and reprecipitating by HCl. Its monosodium salt solution (0.005 *M*) was obtained by adding required alkali solution. CO₂-free 0.1770 *N* NaOH, 0.02159 *N* HNO₃ and 1.0 *M* KNO₃ solutions were prepared using G.R. grade chemicals.

Procedure : The mixtures (i) 0.002159 *N* HNO₃; (ii) 0.001 *M* ligand + (i); (iii) 0.001 *M* metal nitrate + (ii); (iv) 0.0005 *M* metal nitrate + (ii) and (v) 0.001 *M* metal nitrate + ligand pair (each 0.001 *M* concentration) + (i), were titrated pH-metrically⁹ at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.10 *M* (KNO₃). The titration curves were plotted by using experimental data to obtain pH vs moles of alkali used per mole of ligand (*a*) curves (titration curves) which were further utilized to analyze the existing equilibria and to evaluate the corresponding equilibrium constants⁹.

[Cu(ca)(nn)(H₂O)₂].2H₂O : The pH of aqueous equimolar mixtures containing metal nitrate ca-nn (5.0 g Cu(NO₃)₂.2.5H₂O) in water (200 ml) was maintained at 7.5 using NaOH and HNO₃ solutions. The resulting solution was concentrated, kept for crystallization and filtered. The black-brown crystals of the product (washed with very small amount of water followed by ether and dried, yield 56.5%) were found insoluble in common organic solvents but highly soluble in water. Composition of [Cu(ca)(nn)(H₂O)₂].2H₂O was established by elemental analyses

(Found : C, 36.36; H, 3.62; N, 2.67. Calcd. C, 36.48; H, 3.61; N, 2.66%).

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